

EFFECT OF WATER/CEMENT RATIO AND CURING TIME ON COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF MWCNT-CEMENT MORTAR

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ABSTRACT

The present study analyzed the compressive strength enhancement effect of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (hereafter MWCNTs) in ordinary Portland cement (hereafter OPC) mortar by applying an MWCNT solution to OPC mortar. Four parameters were selected as the experimental parameters to affect the compressive strength of MWCNT–cement composites. The experimental parameters include the MWCNT concentration, W/C (water/cement ratio, hereafter W/C), curing age, and MWCNT concentration control methods. The MWCNT concentration was varied from 0.25wt% to 1.0wt%, and W/C was varied from 0.35 to 0.70. The curing age was divided into 7, 14, and 28 days. For the MWCNT concentration control method, a method of creating an MWCNT solution by adjusting the content in the phase of mixing MWCNT with water and a method of controlling the concentration by mixing distilled water with a high concentration of MWCNT solution were compared. The compressive strength of MWCNT–cement composites considering aforementioned parameters was compared against the strength of OPC mortar. In this study, scanning electron microscope (SEM) was also applied to investigate microstructure of the MWCNT cement samples.

1 INTRODUCTION

Studies on mixing various types of fibers with outstanding mechanical properties are being actively studied to improve the mechanical performance of cementitious materials. Accordingly, research and development on next-generation construction materials that combine nanotechnology and construction material began in the mid-2000s. Construction material performance improvement using nanotechnology, however, is still at an early stage. Hence, in the present stage, combining nanotechnology, which has infinite development possibilities, with construction material is necessary.

The present study combines cement with carbon nanotubes (hereafter CNTs), which can improve the compressive performance of cement material due to their outstanding mechanical properties. CNTs can be divided into single-walled carbon nanotubes (hereafter SWCNTs) and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (hereafter MWCNTs). Although SWCNTs have higher Young's modulus, strength, and thermal conductivity as compared to MWCNTs, their industrial use is limited owing to the difficulty of its mass production and high cost. MWCNTs lack some of the desirable material properties of SWCNTs; however, they are still considered a useful material because of their relatively low cost, convenient production, and easy dispersion. Hence, it is more advantageous for application as a cement composite in terms of practicality. Under this circumstance, many researchers have tried to incorporate MWCNTs to cementitious composite.

Nearly all studies to date have focused on the effect of MWCNT concentration on the compressive strength of MWCNT–cement composites. As analyzed in the aforementioned literature studies, well-established research results on the compressive strength of mortar mixed with CNTs have not been reported. Furthermore, the reported results vary even for the same parameters.

The aim of the present study is to analyze the strength improvement effect when cement mortar is mixed with MWCNTs, which have outstanding mechanical properties. To this end, specimens are created using the same mix method for four experimental parameters, all of which is predicted to affect the compressive strength of MWCNT-cement composites. The first considered parameter is the MWCNT concentration by the weight percentage of cement, which varies from 0.25wt% to 1.0wt%. Secondly, curing age is considered as one of experimental parameters covering 7, 14, and 28 days. The next parameter is the ratio of water to cement (W/C) varying from 0.35 to 0.70. Lastly, the MWCNT concentration control method is compared. A method of creating an MWCNT solution by adjusting the content in the phase of mixing MWCNT with water and a method of controlling the concentration by mixing distilled water with a high concentration of MWCNT solution are compared. A total number of 170 mortar cube specimens are fabricated and tested to evaluate the compressive strength under considered parameters. The microstructure within the MWCNT cement is also analyzed through concrete petrography (SEM) as a part of this study.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

When fabricating mortar by mixing MWCNTs with cement, it is essential to disperse the MWCNT solution uniformly within the cement mortar. Because MWCNTs consist of bonds between carbon atoms, they are hydrophobic, and hence dispersion in the cement composite is unlikely to be uniform. In the present study, chemical surface treatment using a surfactant was used to solve this problem [12]. An MWCNT solution was fabricated using sonication treatment [6]. The dispersion of the MWCNTs was confirmed through SEM. The MWCNTs used in the present study had a length of 15 μm and a diameter of 5 nm.

The cube specimens of 50 mm \times 50 mm \times 50 mm for the compressive strength test were fabricated in accordance with the cement compressive strength test standard suggested by ASTM C-109 [13]. Prior to fabricating the mortar specimen, foreign matter and moisture in the cube mold, tamping rod, and the mixer required for fabricating mortar specimens were removed, and Portland cement (Type 1) and standard sand were mixed at a weight ratio of 1:2.5. The MWCNT solution's ratio against the cement weight (W/C) was ranged from 0.35 to 0.70. The mixture of MWCNTs with water, cement, and standard sand were mixed for 4 min in a mixer with a maximum electric power of 700 W. The cement mortar was then placed in a mold and compacted for approximately 20 seconds. Once compacted, the specimens were then stored in a temperature chamber for 24 hours followed by water curing to the specified curing age. After water curing, all moisture on the specimen surface was dried and the by-products were removed. Fig. 1 shows the completed MWCNT mortar specimens and the OPC mortar specimens. The compressive strength tests were conducted by setting the specimens on the Universal Testing Machine (UTM). The experiment was controlled at a rate of 1 mm/min using the displacement-control method.

Figure 1: Mortar specimens.

3 TEST PARAMETERS

As previously mentioned, the present study experimentally analyzed the specimens according to

MWCNT concentration, W/C, curing age, and MWCNT concentration control method. Five specimens were prepared for each parameter and their compressive strengths were measured. To minimize variation and obtain reliable experimental results, the compressive strength was calculated using three average values of the strength test and excluding the maximum and minimum values.

Parameter group	Specimens name	Nano	Concentration (%)	W/C (wt%)	Curing age (day)
Group 1	N-WC35-7	-	-	0.35	7
	N-WC40-7	-	-	0.40	
	N-WC45-7	-	-	0.45	
	N-WC50-7	-	-	0.50	
	N-WC55-7	-	-	0.55	
	N-WC60-7	-	-	0.60	
	N-WC65-7	-	-	0.65	
	N-WC70-7	-	-	0.70	
Group 2	N-WC40-14	-	-	0.4	14
	N-WC50-14	-	-	0.5	
	N-WC60-14	-	-	0.6	
	N-WC40-28	-	-	0.4	28
	N-WC50-28	-	-	0.5	
	N-WC60-28	-	-	0.6	
Group 3	C-10-WC35-7	MWCNT	1.0	0.35	7
	C-10-WC40-7	MWCNT	1.0	0.40	
	C-10-WC45-7	MWCNT	1.0	0.45	
	C-10-WC50-7	MWCNT	1.0	0.50	
	C-10-WC55-7	MWCNT	1.0	0.55	
	C-10-WC60-7	MWCNT	1.0	0.60	
	C-10-WC65-7	MWCNT	1.0	0.65	
	C-10-WC70-7	MWCNT	1.0	0.70	
Group 4	C-10-WC40-14	MWCNT	1.0	0.40	14
	C-10-WC50-14	MWCNT	1.0	0.50	
	C-10-WC60-14	MWCNT	1.0	0.60	
	C-10-WC40-28	MWCNT	1.0	0.40	28
	C-10-WC50-28	MWCNT	1.0	0.50	
	C-10-WC60-28	MWCNT	1.0	0.60	
Group 5	C-1005-WC50-7	MWCNT	1.0 → 0.5	0.50	7
	C-07505-WC50-7	MWCNT	0.75 → 0.5	0.50	
	C-05-WC50-7	MWCNT	0.5	0.50	
Group 6	C-075-WC50-7	MWCNT	0.75	0.50	7
	C-05-WC50-7	MWCNT	0.50	0.50	
	C-025-WC50-7	MWCNT	0.25	0.50	

Table 1: Test parameters.

Table 1 indicates the experiment parameters, which are divided into six groups. The first group was fabricated using OPC mortar specimens with increasing W/C from 0.35 to 0.70 at 0.05 intervals to

compare the early-age strength of specimens cured for 7. The second group compared the compressive strength of 14 days curing and 28 days curing using varying W/C of 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6. The third group was identical to the first group except that it compared the early-age strength of specimens with varying W/C mixed with 1.0wt% of MWCNT and cured for 7 days. The fourth group was identical to the second group except that it used cement mixed with 1.0wt% MWCNTs. In other words, the compressive strength of samples cured for 14 and 28 days when the W/C of the MWCNT mortar specimen was 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6 was measured. In the fifth group, distilled water was added to MWCNT solution with the concentrations of 1.0wt% and 0.75wt% to adjust the MWCNT concentration to 0.5wt%. To compare just the concentration adjustment method, the W/C and curing age of the fifth group were fixed to 0.5 and 7 days, respectively. Finally, the compressive strength of the sixth group was analyzed by fixing the W/C and curing age at 0.5 and 7 days, respectively, while varying the MWCNT concentration as 0.25wt%, 0.5wt%, and 0.75wt%. The specimens in the present study were named in terms of the major parameter, as given in Table 1.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 2 compares the compressive strengths of OPC mortar and the mortar with 1.0wt% MWCNTs cured for 7 days. In general, the compressive strength decreased as W/C increased. The strength of MWCNT mortar was found to be lower than that of ordinary mortar when W/C was 0.55 or greater. When W/C was 0.4, the strength of the MWCNT mortar was 25% greater than that of ordinary mortar. In the meantime, the strength of the MWCNT mortar was 48% lower than that of ordinary mortar when W/C was 0.70. It is considered that compressive strength decreased because for specimens with high water content, MWCNTs interrupt hydration within the cement at the initial stages of curing, and thereby induce weak coherence between hydration materials. From a series of compressive strength tests, the threshold ratio of water and cement was 0.4 when the MWCNT concentration was 1.0wt% in this test.

Fig. 3 shows the compressive strength of OPC mortar and MWCNT mortar as a function of curing age. The compressive strengths of OPC mortar and MWCNT mortar increased as the curing age increased for all considered W/C. The improvement in strength was greater in the mortar with added MWCNT than in OPC mortar as the curing age increased. The strength improvement was significant between 7 days and 14 days for the MWCNT mortar. The MWCNT mortar had greater compressive strength after 28 days of curing than OPC mortar by 34%, 8%, and 4% when W/C was 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6, respectively. It is clear that the MWCNT mortar with low W/C exhibited more effective strength improvement than higher W/C. This is because the MWCNTs in the MWCNT mortar had a bridging effect on the voids among the hydration material with lower water content than higher water content, thereby increasing coherence inside the cement mortar.

Figure 2: Compressive strength (W/C).

Figure 3: Compressive strength (Curing age).

For the MWCNT concentration control method, a method of creating an MWCNT solution by adjusting the content in the phase of mixing MWCNT with water and a method of controlling the

concentration by mixing distilled water with a high concentration of MWCNT solution were compared. Specimens whose concentrations had been adjusted to 0.5wt% were fabricated by mixing distilled water into 1.0wt% and 0.75wt% MWCNT solutions to analyze the strength changes that appear when water is mixed with MWCNTs. As shown in Fig. 4, the compressive strength of each was compared with that of a control group specimen fabricated using an original MWCNT solution of 0.5wt% concentration. It was observed that the difference between the test group and the control group was less than 5%, which implies that mixing distilled water into MWCNTs does not affect the strength. Thus, the strength of the MWCNT mortar is minimally affected even if a solution of lower concentration is fabricated by mixing distilled water into a MWCNT solution of a certain concentration.

Fig. 5 presents the compressive strength results of MWCNT mortar cured for 7 days as a function of various MWCNT concentrations. The compressive strength tended to increase somewhat as the MWCNT solution concentration increased. The compressive strength was approximately 26% greater when the MWCNT concentration was 1.0wt% than when the MWCNT concentration was 0.25wt%. In other words, even if the MWCNT concentration is four times greater, the increase in compressive strength is merely 26%. This implies that lower concentration can sometimes be more effective to reach the desirable strength. It should be noted that the test results given in this study are valid for relatively early-age (7 day) mortar. Research on the relationship between concentration of MWCNT and compressive strength for completely hardened mortar (28 days or more) is currently underway.

Figure 4: Compressive strength (Control).

Figure 5: Compressive strength (Concentration).

5 SEM CROSS-SECTIONAL IMAGE

The present study analyzed MWCNT mortar samples using SEM to rationally investigate the bridging effect between microcracks and the degree of MWCNT dispersion in the cement. Fig. 6 depicts the cross-sectional image of C-10-WC40-28, which showed a significant improvement in strength as compared to OPC mortar. An image of the identical section was analyzed in detail based on various magnifications. The image in Fig. 6(a) shows MWCNTs dispersed into the cement at 5,000 times magnification. Fig. 6(b) shows randomly dispersed MWCNTs in the cement magnified 10,000 times, whereas Fig. 6(c) is the same image magnified 30,000 times.

The magnified image shows the hexagonal habit of calcium hydroxide, needle-like habit of ettringite, and the sheet-like habit of calcium-silicate-hydrate (C-S-H). The cross-sectional image also shows effective dispersion of MWCNT in the cement mortar without agglomeration, and the cement was settled with chemical products such as C-S-H and calcium hydroxide. Fig. 6(c) shows the evidence of MWCNT bridging the crack gap in cement mortar. The C-S-H exists in the form of stand-alone clusters, joined together by many needle-like hydrates. Furthermore, calcium hydroxides are distributed among the cement mortar. MWCNTs are observed around pores and microcracks. It is widely known that microcracks and porosity localize stress concentration. Since the strength is negatively influenced by the pore content, the improvement of strength is due to a reduction of porosity in the

cement mortar. The study confirmed that MWCNTs appear to improve the compressive strength of MWCNT-cement composites through a bridging effect with the hydration materials.

Figure 6: SEM images of C-10-WC40-28.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The present study conducted experiments for improving the compressive strength of cement mortar by adding MWCNTs. To analyze the parameters that affect the strength of MWCNT cement mortar during production, a total number of 170 mortar cube specimens were fabricated and tested using MWCNT concentration, W/C, curing age, and MWCNT concentration adjustment methods as experimental parameters. The following conclusions were derived based on the experiment results.

- (1) The compressive strength of MWCNT mortar was generally greater than that of OPC mortar. This appears to be because, as the curing age increases, MWCNT is dispersed above the hydration material like a net, preventing the progression of microcracks through a bridging effect between microcracks within the cement mortar. Moreover, compressive strength increased as porosity decreased by reducing the space between the voids of the hydration material.
- (2) The compressive strength of specimens cured for 7 days and with W/C above 0.55 was greater for the OPC mortar. The compressive strength tended to improve with increased curing age when W/C was 0.5 and 0.6; however, once the curing period elapsed, effective dispersion of MWCNTs led to a compressive strength greater than that of OPC mortar.
- (3) Analysis of compressive strength for various MWCNT solution concentrations ranging from 0.25wt% to 1.0wt% showed that higher concentrations of MWCNTs enhanced the compressive strength of cement. The increase in compressive strength, however, was not linearly proportional to the increase in MWCNT concentration. In the present study, a four-fold increase in MWCNT concentration led to a 26% increase in strength.
- (4) When lowering the MWCNT concentration by adding distilled water to an aqueous MWCNT solution (in other words, by adjusting the concentration of 1.0% or 0.75% to 0.5%), the change in compressive strength was insignificant as compared to that of an MWCNT solution mixed to a concentration of 0.5%. This appears to be because the added distilled water has a relatively insignificant impact on agglomeration or dispersion because the existing MWCNT solution was fabricated using distilled water, and thus changes in the strength of the cement are minimal.
- (5) Analysis of the microstructure of the MWCNT cement using SEM showed uniform dispersion of the MWCNTs while not interrupting the generation of hydration materials such as C-S-H, calcium hydroxide, and ettringite.
- (6) Parameters comparing the early-age compressive strength of 7-days curing need to be tested for the compressive strength of 28-days curing and comparatively analyzed with the compressive strength

of OPC mortar for future studies. Moreover, because the MWCNT concentration was fixed above 1.0wt% during the experiment, relatively low MWCNT concentrations should be further tested to find the optimum threshold concentration for MWCNT-cement composites.

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